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Effective Teaching And Learning Of Business Studies As Perceived By Teachers In Junior Secondary Schools In Delta Central Senatorial District

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ABSTRACT

This study examined effective teaching and learning of Business Studies as perceived by teachers in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial District. Four research questions were raised and four hypotheses were equally formulated in line with the specific objectives of the study and tested at 0.05 level of significant. Several literature were reviewed for the study alongside the theoretical framework provided to explain the facts generated in the study. Vygotsky's theory of Scaffolding was adopted for the study. The descriptive survey design was utilized in this study. Population of the study was 281 business studies teachers from junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial District. The sample size was 281, hence, the sampling technique adopted was census sampling. Self-structured questionnaire was used to collect information from the respondents. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and the hypotheses of the study were tested using t-test and ANOVA. The findings of the study revealed that effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts is faced with several problems such as insufficient teaching/instructional materials, unconducive classroom environment for teaching and learning, inadequate funding and so on. Also, that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female business studies teachers on problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts among others. The study recommended that Government should provide adequate fund to purchase sufficient teaching/instructional materials, build conducive classroom environment/computer laboratory for effective teaching and learning of Business studies among others.

Keywords: Business Studies, instructional materials, learning

INTRODUCTION

The goal of business studies in secondary education is to give students a foundational understanding of the subject and spark their interest in it so that they will desire to pursue business studies beyond secondary school. One of the most important instruments available to a person for self-development is education. The goal of education is to prepare students for self-reliance and success in the business world. It is training for meaningful employment in trade, industries, agriculture, technical fields, and business, among other areas. The focus is mostly on business. Since

the 1980s, business studies have been a crucial component of vocational and technical education, which is a requirement for secondary school education in Nigeria. The goal of including vocational and technical education into the secondary school curriculum was to give the pupils the tools they needed to become self-sufficient. In light of these national goals, the "6-3-3-4" system of education—also known as the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013)—was developed. Students will spend six years in elementary school, three years in junior secondary school (JSS), three years in senior secondary school (SSS), and four years in postsecondary education, according to the new system's innovations (Omotayo, Ihebereme & Maduwesi, 2008).

Okolocha and Onyeneke (2013) state that the goal of the several reform agendas, particularly those pertaining to the secondary school system, is to address the issue of disparities in educational access and quality. As a result, new curriculum in pre-vocational topics such as "Agriculture, Business Studies, Home Economics, Computer Education, Fine Arts and Music" were created for junior secondary education (FRN, 2013). The main goals of business studies in junior secondary schools were to give pupils a thorough understanding of the business world and to improve their proficiency in typing, bookkeeping, office procedures, shorthand, and commerce. Combining these topics was intended to assume learning, connect real-world experiences to the classroom, and increase students' awareness of their educational sensitivity (Zakari, 2006). According to Paul (2003), the nation's educational system offers the broad foundation for developing policies that will direct the advancement of vocational education and training in the future. As a result, the strategy offers precise guidelines for the advancement of business courses in secondary education going forward. The main goal of including business studies in secondary school curricula, according to Shuga (2010), was to give pupils the knowledge, abilities, and attitudes they would need to succeed in secondary school, the workforce, postsecondary education or training, and everyday life.

Eze (2011) added that the goals of the business studies curriculum are to enable students to gain an understanding of business concepts through the study of subjects such as commerce, shorthand, office practice, book keeping and typewriting. to also help to Develop the skills, including critical thinking skills, and strategies required for self-employment .To Apply the knowledge, skills, and attitudes acquired through the study of business to a variety of learning tasks and relate them to business phenomena on the local, national, and global levels; To Develop lifelong learning skills that will help students adapt to technological advancements, the changing workplace, and the global economy; To Make connections that will help students take advantage of potential postsecondary educational, work, and business opportunities. After introducing the objectives of 6.3.3.4 system of education, Suobere (2008), opined that there is doubt whether the objectives are realized, and he observed that the skills and knowledge provided to secondary school students are not yielding the desired objectives.

Yamada (2007) opined that graduates of secondary schools in Nigeria have little or no skills for self-reliant. From the study of existing literature, most research reports about business studies in secondary schools revealed that the implemented curriculum do not favor achieving the desired objectives. This prompted the researcher to investigate the "Perception of teachers and students on problems of effective teaching and learning and their remedies. Business studies focuses on the welfare of individuals, families and societies, it also contributes meaningfully to the solutions of the problems of the society such as unemployment, poverty, and malnutrition. Business studies as a vocational subject is required to equip the learner with the knowledge of skill and attitude necessary for thre effective management of the home, it requires skills, wisdom, dedication, care, intelligence, unusual patience and very strong power of observation and imagination. Therefore, a student that has these qualities should study vocational/ business subjects especially business studies from secondary school to help harness those skills rather the opposite. Federal Government wants business studies to occupy a prominent position in our secondary schools. Unfortunately, Nigerian schools pay little or no attention to vocational/business subjects. Teachers and students seem not to understand what it is all about and consequently, develop some contempt and aversion for the subjects. Many of the occupations and trades are regarded as ignoble and unbecoming.

An average Nigerian parents does not want his son to earn a living as a full time farmer, a watch-repairer, a plumber, a house painter, for many Nigerians, these jobs are for the poor and underprivileged. Typically, the higher the occupational status of the students' parents, the more positive their attitude towards learning. This is to say that higher the occupation of the parents or guardian the more they would want their child to be learned, educated etc. without considering if the child would actually read the subject or courses to achieve that. The influence of parents in the development of students' interest in business studies subjects cannot be over emphasized this is because parent seem to have much influence on children's choice of educational career. The socio-economic status of parent of a child determines the type of career one choose to do, some parents have biased and rigid thoughts regarding the occupational choices of a child/children. Parents often forgot that every type of work is beneficial to the individual and society, is worthy and noble. The quality sign of potential success in students vocational and business pursuits require the identification of the students interest, aptitudes, abilities, values and judgments, if these will be discovered, it requires a guidance counselor who will give the appropriate occupational information to the student with proper exposition to various opportunities available in the world of work. It is not a surprise that some students are not interested in business studies subjects. it is said that our society and economic problem is a national attitude that implies the business subjects are designed for somebody else's children and is meant primarily for the children of the poor. This same attitude is shared by students. Thus, it makes the students lack interest in the study of business subjects. The skill that teachers exhibit in teaching influences the student enrolment in vocational/business subject the method of approach is very important in any teaching/learning situation. The way the teacher presents the subject matter to the learner may make a student like or dislike a subject. The need for blending theoretical and practical work in teaching of business subjects (studies) as to stimulate students' interest more especially on vocational and business subjects. The greatest single factor in teaching learning is the teacher. No technique, no method, no device, no gadget can guarantee success, but only an effective qualified teacher can adequately execute these. Thus the greatest motivating device yet discovered is the highly motivated teacher and the students are to be involved actively in teaching and learning process in a way of projects, field trips, directed field activities etc., note learning and subject centered orientation should be changed to a more practical and child centered method. The increase in qualities and quantities of outputs should be primarily due to improvement in the quality of the teacher. It is therefore the trust of this study to explore the teachers perception as well as the students perception and the problem affecting effective teaching and learning on the study of business studies in Nigerian secondary schools.

The broad aims of secondary education according to Nigeria National Policy on Education, FRN (2004), are preparation of students for useful living within the society and for higher education. Specifically, secondary education is to: Provide a higher level of education for all primary school leavers, offer diversified curricular to provide for all, provide sub-professional manpower in science, technology and commerce field, provide technical knowledge and vocational skills, inspire desire for self-improvement and achievement and raise citizens who can think and respect the views of others.

The problem with our 6-3-3-4 system of education is that, it seems to lack proper focus, guidance and directions for our youths (students) and is too theoretical. In line with this, the growth of our education sector is mainly in size and not in quality hence, the education system of Nigeria is yet to meet the challenges of preparing students for the contemporary global world. The quality of our education with its emphasis on theory more than practical has resulted in production of graduates with unemployable skills leading to unprecedented increase in different types of crimes in the country. According to Nwadiani (2012), "the low relevance and poor quality of education in Nigeria akin to schooling or learning shock, educational system failure, dystrophies and dysfunction, are traceable to some observable rots there from the service delivery".

According to Okoro (2023) Self-reliance and job sustainability proffer remedies to the present unemployment problem in Nigeria and it is on this basis that business education provides the undergraduate students with the practice oriented knowledge and strategies required in specific occupation. Education is a process in which knowledge, belief, skills and cultural value are shared

from one generation to another (Oroka & Igberaharha, 2008). According to Becker (1997), many business students find it difficult to apply economic principles after studying business concepts. It is therefore, imperative now to find ways and means of making the teaching and learning of the subject more effective.

Statement of the problem

Business studies has been acknowledged as a means for transforming and empowering youths, therefore grooming the students at early stage to be self-reliant, self-employed, creative and innovative. In recent times student lack interest in business studies, even after being taught in secondary school they will not want to further their course on business studies, thereby creating low numbers of students who apply to study business education in the university. This has led to reduction in the number of business education graduates who in turn are supposed to teacher the younger generation business studies.

What could be the factors affecting the effective teaching of business studies in junior secondary schools? Could it be that employers find it difficult to get business studies graduate as teachers to teach business studies in schools? Could it be that government is not employing teachers for the subject? Could it be that there are inadequate instructional materials to teach the subject? Could it be that students do not find business studies interesting, making them to lack interest in learning the subject? Or could it be that business studies teachers lack motivation for teaching the subject?

The need to provide answers to these questions motivated the researcher to carry out this study which is effective teaching and learning of Business Studies as perceived by teachers in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts.

Research Questions

The following research question were raised as guide to the study.

- i. What are the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts?
- ii. What are the causes of the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts?
- iii. What are the perceptions of teachers to the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools Delta Central Senatorial Districts?
- iv. What are the strategies in curbing the problems of teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts?

Purpose of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine effective teaching and learning of Business Studies as perceived by teachers in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts. The specific objectives of this study are to:

- i. Investigate the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts.
- ii. Examine the causes of the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts.
- iii. Ascertain the perception of teachers to the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts.
- iv. Determine the strategies in curbing the problems of teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study.

- i. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female business studies teachers on problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts.
- ii. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of business studies teachers on causes of the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts based on educational qualification.

- iii. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of business studies teachers on perceptions of teachers to the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary school in Delta Central Senatorial Districts based on work experience.
- iv. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of business studies teachers on strategies in curbing the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts based on work experience.

RESEARCH METHOD AND PROCEDURE

This section outlines the methods employed to achieve the research objectives, detailed under following subheadings: Area of the Study, Research Design, Population of the Study, Sample and Sampling Technique, Research Instrument, Validity of the Research Instrument, Reliability of the Research Instrument, Method of Data Collection, and Method of Data Analysis.

Area of the Study

Delta Central Senatorial District is one of the three senatorial districts in Delta State, Nigeria. It is made up of eight local government areas. These are Ehioppe East, Ehioppe West, Okpe, Sapele, Udu, Ughelli North, Ughelli South, Uvwie. The Delta Central Senatorial District has a diverse population comprising of various ethnic groups, predominantly the Urhobo people. The region is characterized by a mix of urban and rural communities, with agriculture, trade, and education being the primary economic activities.

Research Design

A descriptive survey research design was utilized in this study. This design systematically gathers data from a target population using structured research instruments. As noted by Okorodudu (2013), when selecting an appropriate research design for a project, dissertation, or thesis, one must consider whether the research interest is experimental or non-experimental. If it is non-experimental, a descriptive research design is appropriate. Therefore, the descriptive survey research design is deemed suitable for this study because the researcher does not manipulate variables and conditions.

Population of the Study

The target population of the study was all public junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts made up of 281 Business Studies Teachers. This data was obtained from Department of Records and Statistics, Post Primary Education Board, Asaba, Delta State as shown in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Population Distribution of Business Studies Teachers in Public Junior Secondary Schools in Delta Central Senatorial District.

S/N	Local Government Area	Number of Business Studies Teachers
1.	Ehioppe East	22
2.	Ehioppe West	11
3.	Okpe	25
4.	Sapele	36
5.	Udu	41
6.	Ughelli North	50
7.	Ughelli South	32
8.	Uvwie	64
	Total	281

Source: Post Primary Education Board, Asaba (2024)

Sample and Sampling Technique

The entire population of 281 business studies teachers was utilized for the study because of the manageable size hence, the census sampling technique was adopted for this study.

Research Instrument

The study's research instrument was a 40-item self-structured questionnaire titled "Effective Teaching and Learning of Business Studies as Perceived by Teachers Questionnaire (ETLBSPTQ)". The questionnaire was broken into two sections. Section A requests information from respondents on their bio-data, whereas Section B contains items to solicit opinion of the respondents regarding the subject matter. Items in Section B were graded on a 4-point Likert type scale of Strongly Agree - 4 points, Agree - 3 points, Disagree - 2 points, and Strongly Disagree – 1 point. (See Appendix II, Pg. 88-91).

Validity of Instrument

The instrument for data collection was validated by three experts - two experts from the Department of Business Education and one expert from Measurement and Evaluation unit of the Delta State University, Abraka. It was also suggested that the demographic variables in the questionnaire be used as moderating variables in hypotheses formulation. Corrections were also made on the use of appropriate punctuation marks, spellings, appropriate paraphrasing on the study to ensure face and content validity before the preparation of the final copy of the instrument. (See Appendix III, Pg. 88-91).

Reliability of the Instrument

To ascertain the reliability of the instrument, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) was used. A pilot study was conducted using 15 Business Studies teachers from Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, which is outside the study area. The reliability coefficient of 0.84 was obtained which signified that the instrument in the scales were reliable. (See Appendix III, Pg. 92).

Method of Data Collection

The researcher with the help of three research assistants administered the questionnaire to the respondents in the junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial District. A total of 281 copies of the questionnaire were distributed twice to the respondents with two weeks interval. The completed copies of the questionnaire were collected immediately in order to ensure high retrieval rate of the distributed instrument.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics in form of frequency count and percentage were used in analyzing the bio data of the respondents while statistical mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD) were used in answering the research questions. While t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used in testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule on the research questions was based on the criterion mean of 2.50, where any calculated mean that is less than 2.50 was regarded as disagree and any calculated mean that was 2.50 and above was considered as agree. For the null hypothesis, any calculated p-value that was less than or equal to 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected while any calculated p-value that was greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was retained.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study are tabulated as follows:

Research Question 1: What are the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts?

Table 4.1: Mean and Standard Deviation responses of business studies teachers on problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	X	SD	DECISION
	Problems Of Effective Teaching And Learning Of Business Studies			
1.	Insufficient teaching/instructional materials hinder the effective teaching and learning of business studies.	3.05	0.75	Agree
2.	Lack of qualified business studies teachers is a major challenge in junior secondary schools.	2.06	0.73	Disagree
3.	The classroom environment is not conducive for the teaching and learning of business studies.	3.07	0.75	Agree
4.	Inadequate funding affects the availability of resources for business studies.	3.32	0.56	Agree
5.	The curriculum for business studies is outdated and not relevant to the objective of the subject.	3.35	0.57	Agree
6.	Large class sizes obstruct students' attention in teaching and learning of business studies.	3.33	0.59	Agree
7.	Poor students' interest and engagement are significant barriers to teaching and learning of business studies.	3.41	0.58	Agree
8.	Limited access to practical training and real-world applications affects the quality of business studies.	3.34	0.56	Agree
9.	Teachers' absenteeism is a problem that impacts the consistency of business studies.	3.25	0.71	Agree
10.	Inadequate infrastructure, such as insufficient classrooms or lack of computer laboratories, hinders effective teaching and learning of business studies	3.37	0.57	Agree
	Grand Mean/SD	3.16	0.64	Agree

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Data presented in Table 4.1 shows that nine out of the ten items on the scale mean responses of respondents on problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts ranged from 3.05 to 3.41 which indicates that the respondents agreed that they are problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies while the respondents disagreed to item 2 with mean rating of 2.06. This indicates that there are qualified business studies teachers in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial district. However, the standard deviation ranged from 0.56 to 0.75. Similarly, the grand mean of 3.16 depicts that teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts is faced with several problems. Also, the standard deviation shows that the respondents are not far apart in their responses to the criterion mean of 2.50.

Research Question 2: *What are the causes of the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts?*

Table 4.2: Mean and Standard Deviation responses of business studies teachers on causes of the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	X	SD	DECISION
	Causes Of The Problems Of Effective Teaching And Learning Of Business Studies			
11.	Insufficient government funding is a primary cause of the challenges in teaching and learning business studies.	3.11	0.81	Agree
12.	Lack of teacher training and development programmes contributes to the ineffectiveness of business studies.	3.35	0.57	Agree
13.	Inadequate infrastructure and facilities are major causes of poor teaching and learning conditions.	3.40	0.58	Agree
14.	Poor socio-economic factors of students' families affect their ability to afford necessary learning materials.	3.33	0.59	Agree
15.	The curriculum is not aligned with current industry demands making business studies less relevant.	3.43	0.58	Agree
16.	Poor cultural attitudes towards business education influence students' and parents' value placed on subject.	3.37	0.57	Agree
17.	Administrative inefficiencies in schools contribute to the lack of resources and support for business studies.	3.41	0.58	Agree
18.	High rate of student-to-teacher ratios make it difficult for effective teaching to occur.	3.30	0.64	Agree
19.	Lack of community and industry involvement in education results in a gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application of Business studies.	3.40	0.58	Agree
20.	Inconsistent educational policies and changes in the curriculum disrupt the continuity of business studies.	3.33	0.57	Agree
	Grand Mean/SD	3.34	0.61	Agree

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Data presented in Table 4.2 indicates that the mean responses of respondents on causes of the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts ranged from 3.11 to 3.43 which indicates that the business studies teachers agreed to all the items on the scale as causes of the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools. However, the standard deviation ranged from 0.57 to 0.81. Similarly, the grand mean of 3.34 reveals that all the items on the scales are causes of the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts. Also, the standard deviation shows that the respondents are not far apart in their responses to the criterion mean of 2.50.

Research Question 3: *What are the perceptions of teachers to the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts?*

Table 4.3: Mean and Standard Deviation responses of business studies teachers on perceptions of teachers to the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	X	SD	DECISION
	Teachers' Perception Of The Problems Of Teaching And Learning Of Business Studies			
21.	Lack of continuous professional development for teachers affects their effectiveness in teaching business studies.	3.28	0.61	Agree
22.	Teachers feel that low salaries and incentives demotivate them from delivering quality education.	3.38	0.58	Agree
23.	Poor communication with school administration hinders the resolution of teaching challenges.	3.42	0.59	Agree
24.	The current assessment methods are not effective in evaluating students' performance in business studies.	3.32	0.63	Agree
25.	Teachers believe that parents' lack of involvement affects students' performance in business studies.	3.40	0.58	Agree
26.	Overloaded teaching schedules reduce the quality of instruction provided by teachers.	3.30	0.61	Agree
27.	Teachers perceive that students' poor foundational knowledge is a barrier to effective learning.	3.31	0.63	Agree
28.	Limited access to technology and modern teaching tools affects the delivery of business studies.	3.28	0.64	Agree
29.	The lack of peer collaboration and support among teachers impedes sharing of best practices.	3.37	0.60	Agree
30.	Inadequate training in the use of digital resources for teaching business studies is a significant issue.	3.36	0.62	Agree
	Grand Mean/SD	3.34	0.61	Agree

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Data presented in Table 4.3 shows that the mean responses of respondents on perceptions of teachers to the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts ranged from 3.28 to 3.42 which indicates that the business studies teachers perceived that all the items in the scale are problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies. However, the standard deviation ranged from 0.58 to 0.64. Similarly, the grand mean of 3.34 depicts that business studies teachers perceived that effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts is faced with numerous problems. Also, the standard deviation shows that the respondents are very close in their responses to the criterion mean of 2.50.

Research Question 4: *What are the strategies in curbing the problems of teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts?*

Table 4.4: Mean and Standard Deviation responses of business studies teachers on strategies in curbing the problems of teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Decision
	Strategies To Curbing The Problems Of Effective Teaching And Learning Of Business Education			
31.	Increasing funding and resources for business studies is essential for improving teaching and learning	3.04	0.78	Agree
32.	Regular professional development programmes for teachers can enhance their teaching skills.	3.32	0.56	Agree
33.	Upgrading and maintaining school infrastructure will create a better learning environment.	3.40	0.58	Agree
34.	Updating the business studies curriculum to reflect current industry trends is necessary.	3.33	0.59	Agree
35.	Reducing class sizes can improve the quality of interaction between teachers and students.	3.44	0.58	Agree
36.	Incorporating more practical exercises and real-world applications in the curriculum will enhance teaching and learning.	3.36	0.56	Agree
37.	Improving teacher incentives and working conditions can motivate teachers to perform better.	3.28	0.69	Agree
38.	Strengthening parent-teacher communication can help address students' challenges in business studies.	3.39	0.57	Agree
39.	Leveraging technology in teaching, such as using digital tools and online resources, will improve educational delivery.	3.38	0.57	Agree
40.	Encouraging community and industry partnerships can provide students with practical experiences and mentorship opportunities.	3.60	0.54	Strongly Agree
	Grand Mean/SD	3.35	0.60	Agree

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Data presented in Table 4.4 reveals that nine out of the ten items on the scale mean responses of respondents on strategies in curbing the problems of teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts ranged from 3.04 to 3.44 which indicates that the business studies teachers agreed to these items on the scale as strategies in curbing the problems of teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools.

Similarly, the respondents strongly agreed to item 40 as strategies in curbing the problems of teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools. Similarly, the grand mean of 3.35 shows that all the items on the scales are strategies in curbing the problems of teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts. Correspondingly, the standard deviation ranged from 0.57 to 0.81. shows that the respondents are not far apart in their responses to the criterion mean of 2.50.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings on research question one revealed that effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts is faced with several problems such as insufficient teaching/instructional materials, unconducive classroom environment for teaching and learning, inadequate funding, outdated curriculum, large class sizes, poor students' interest and engagement, limited access to practical training and real-world applications, teachers' absenteeism and inadequate infrastructure such as insufficient classrooms or lack of computer laboratories. This findings is in harmony with Nwaukwa and Okonkwo (2019) who found that classroom management and provision of modern technological equipment and facilities were rated effective for teaching of business subjects in secondary schools. This finding support Osaige (2015) that there is dearth of qualified teachers for vocational and business subjects, poor infrastructure, and lack of equipment, instructional materials and books. Also, that the schools were not adequately financed.

The findings on research question two shows causes of the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts as insufficient government funding, lack of teacher training and development programmes, inadequate infrastructure and facilities, poor socio-economic factors of students' families, curriculum not aligned with current industry demands, poor cultural attitudes towards business studies, administrative inefficiencies, high rate of student-to-teacher ratios, lack of community and industry involvement in education, and inconsistent educational policies and changes in the curriculum. This finding is in agreement with that of Julie and Josephine (2015) as cited in Seyi (2023) found that inadequacies in the curriculum content of business subjects, time allocation, non-relevance of course/subject content, lack of or inadequate educational facilities, dearth of business teacher motivation are contemporary issues affecting teaching and learning of business subject

The findings on research question three indicates that business studies teachers perceived that effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts is faced with numerous problems such as, lack of continuous professional development for teachers which affects their effectiveness in teaching business studies, low salaries and incentives which demotivate teachers from delivering quality education, poor communication with school administration hinders the resolution of teaching challenges, ineffectiveness of the current assessment methods in evaluating students' performance in business studies, parents' lack of involvement affects students' performance in business studies, Overloaded teaching schedules, students' poor foundational knowledge is a barrier to effective learning, limited access to technology and modern teaching tools, lack of peer collaboration and support among teachers and inadequate training in the use of digital resources for teaching business studies. The finding is in harmony with Okolocha and Onyeneke (2013) who found that principals' perception of business studies teachers were that the teachers were ineffective in holding to some aspects of time management; classroom management and lesson note preparation and delivery for optimal achievement of instructional goals and improved students' academic achievements and consequently employability. Further, the findings equally indicate that gender, and teacher experiences do not have influence on business studies teachers' teaching effectiveness in secondary schools in the State.

The findings on research question four indicates strategies in curbing the problems of teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts. These strategies includes: Increasing funding and resources for business studies, regular professional development programmes for teachers, upgrading and maintaining school infrastructures, updating the business studies curriculum to reflect current industry trends, reducing class sizes, incorporating more practical exercises and real-world applications in the curriculum, improving teacher incentives and working conditions, strengthening parent-teacher communication, leveraging technology in teaching, and encouraging community and industry partnerships. This finding is in line with that of finding support Emeasoba and Igwe (2016) that business studies teachers in Enugu State junior secondary school teachers regarded interactive instructional strategies as effective and also considered experimental instructional strategies as very effective for teaching business studies.

The findings of hypothesis one indicated that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female business studies teachers on problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts. The finding support Okolocha and Onyeneke (2013) who found that that gender do not have influence on business studies teachers' teaching effectiveness in secondary schools in the State.

Also, this finding is in consonant with Emeasoba and Igwe (2016) that found in their study that there was no significance difference in the mean rating of male and female business teachers on the effectiveness of direct institutional strategies for teaching business studies at the junior secondary school level. Further, the finding contradicted that of Nwaukwa and Okonkwo (2019) who found that gender significantly affect respondents mean rating on Business teachers' strategies for effective teaching of business subjects in secondary schools in Umuahia Educational Zone, Abia State. Likewise, the finding disagreed with that of Akanbi (2013) who discovered that gender had a significant main effect on students' entrepreneurship knowledge.

The findings of hypothesis two showed that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of business studies teachers on causes of the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts based on educational qualification. The finding is compatible with Olori and Olajide (2018) that there was no significant difference in the perception of teachers based on teaching qualifications on the usefulness of instructional media to effective teaching of Business Studies.

The findings of hypothesis three indicated that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of less experience and experience business studies teachers on perceptions of teachers to the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary school in Delta Central Senatorial District based on work experience. The finding is consistent with Olori and Olajide (2018) who found that there was no significant difference in the perception of experienced and less experienced teachers on the usefulness of instructional media to effective teaching of business studies.

The findings of hypothesis four displayed that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of less experience and experience business studies teachers on strategies in curbing the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial Districts based on work experience. This finding is in disagreement with Nwaukwa and Okonkwo (2019) who found that years of experience significantly affect respondents mean ratings on Business teachers' strategies for effective teaching of business subjects in secondary schools in Umuahia Educational Zone, Abia State.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that effective teaching and learning of Business studies as perceived by teachers in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial district is faced with numerous problems. It was further concluded that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of business studies teachers on problems, causes, perceptions of teachers and strategies in curbing the problems of effective teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial districts based on gender, educational qualification and work experience.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendation are made:

1. Government should provide adequate fund to purchase sufficient teaching/instructional materials, build conducive classroom environment/computer laboratory for effective teaching and learning of Business studies.
2. School authorities in collaboration with the government and other stakeholders should provide avenue for teachers to development themselves through in-service training, conferences, workshops and seminars as this will enhance the quality of work provided by the teachers.

3. Government should increase salaries and incentives paid to teacher as this will motivate teachers to deliver quality education to the students.
4. Curriculum planners should update the business studies curriculum to reflect current industry trends. As this will make the students to be relevant to the society after understudying business studies at the junior secondary school.
5. Management should note that gender, educational qualification, work experience do not affect the business studies teachers effectiveness in teaching and learning of business studies in junior secondary schools in Delta State.
6. A study of this nature should be replicated in other geographical location for better-quality outcome.

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